

Sound-evoked Fluid Motion at the Apex of the Guinea Pig Cochlea

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Abstract. The inner ear analyses sound-evoked oscillations in the cochlear fluids. However, our knowledge of cochlear fluid dynamics is limited, encompassing primarily measurements of acoustically-evoked pressures from basal regions (*e.g.* Olson, *Nature*, **402**, 526–9 (1999)), with little data available from the fluid inside the organ of Corti. Recent data shows that the apex works differently from the base of the cochlea (Warren *et al.*, *PNAS* **113**, E4304-10 (2016); Recio-Spinoso & Oghalai, *J Physiol.* **595**, 4549-4561 (2017); Burwood *et al.*, *Sci. Adv.*, **8**, eabq2773 (2022)), suggesting that apical fluid dynamics may exhibit characteristics not evident at other locations. Here, we used fluorescence correlation spectroscopy, raster image correlation spectroscopy, and laser tweezers to measure fluid motion and fluid-related forces acting at the apex of the guinea pig cochlea under conditions that primarily reflect passive mechanics. The measurements span locations in the endolymph at different distances from the organ of Corti, as well as the fluid motions in the tunnel of Corti and the spaces of Nuel. We show that the sound power level in scala media is well below 0 dB SWL even for relatively intense stimuli, with even smaller values from the inner sulcus, tunnel of Corti and spaces of Nuel. The implications of these results for apical organ of Corti function will be discussed.

INTRODUCTION

The apex of the cochlea works differently from other cochlear areas. At the base of the cochlea, the best frequency is strongly dependent on the exact location of measurement, so a change in the measurement location by a mere 100 microns will cause a substantial change in the best frequency. In contrast, recent optical coherence tomography measurements show that this type of “place coding” is not present at the apex of the guinea pig cochlea. In the study by Burwood *et al* (1), three different sites located less than 4 mm from the helicotrema were examined in detail. At low stimulus levels, the most apical site had the highest best frequency, whereas the two more basally located sites shared the same best frequency, despite being located several thousand microns from each other. This is not consistent with standard models of cochlear frequency tuning.

Burwood *et al* also examined group delays. In their most sensitive preparations, a negative group delay was observed between the two most basally located sites, meaning that the more apically located site tended to respond earlier to the acoustic stimulus. This is not consistent with a conventional traveling wave, which is assumed to propagate from the base toward the apex. Only at high stimulus levels or after administering agents that abolish active outer hair cell motility did the response at the apex conform to conventional traveling wave theory.

There are additional measurements that document an apical response pattern that differs from the one at the base. Warren *et al* (2) examined the response of the basilar membrane and found that only a restricted region immediately under the base of the outer hair cells exhibited substantial sound-evoked responses. When the measurement location

moved closer to either the lateral wall or the inner hair cells, response amplitudes dropped sharply. As a result, most of the basilar membrane was motionless during sound stimulation.

There are papers that attempt to refute the above findings. Recio-Spinoso *et al* (3) claim to have done so, but we note that only one of their measurement locations was in the same region as the one examined by Burwood *et al*. For the location that was similar, results are in good agreement. As regards group delays, Recio-Spinoso and Oghalai (4) published data showing apical group delays that changed with stimulus level, the group delay difference between their measurement sites approaching zero at low stimulus levels. Thus, it seems to us that the available datasets are in fact in good agreement: The mechanical behavior of the apex is different from the one of the base in many important respects.

Given this mechanical behavior of the apical organ of Corti, we asked whether the apex to base dissimilarities are due to intrinsic differences in hearing organ properties at various cochlear locations, or whether the stimulus that drives hearing organ motion is in some part different?

The hearing organ is driven by the motion and pressure of the fluid, along with forces generated by the outer hair cells. These interact with the passive mechanical properties of the organ of Corti to produce the observed sound-evoked vibrations.

Due to Olson's pioneering work (*e.g.* 5, 6), measurements of fluid motion and pressure are available from the base of the cochlea. Little is known about fluid motion or pressures at the apex. Even less is known about fluid motions and pressures inside the organ of Corti, for any cochlear location. The goal of the present work is to describe methods that make such measurements possible, along with initial results from these measurements.

METHODS

The present measurements were performed on temporal bone preparations isolated from guinea pigs weighing less than 400 g. All animal procedures were approved by the local ethics committee. Animals were deeply anesthetized and then decapitated and their temporal bones, including the middle ear ossicles and the ear canal, were extracted and placed in a plastic holder with the ear canal facing a loudspeaker, allowing acoustic stimulation through the natural pathway. The preparation was then immersed in oxygenated tissue culture medium. Through a small opening in scala tympani at the base of the cochlea, a thin piece of plastic tubing was inserted. The tubing was connected to a reservoir filled with continuously oxygen-bubbled tissue culture medium. This oxygenated fluid flowed through scala tympani, providing the cells of the organ of Corti with a continuous supply of oxygen. The fluid exited through a second opening located in scala vestibuli at the apex.

This preparation has been used in several previous studies (*e.g.* 7,8) and direct comparisons with apical vibrations recorded *in vivo* show preservation of passive mechanics (1, 2). When electrical currents are injected through electrodes placed in scala media, active outer hair cell responses can be restored, including amplification of sound-evoked motion (9). Such current injections were however not used in the present study, meaning that we are here studying cochlear responses that are dominated by passive mechanics. However, we used electrodes in scala media to inject fluorescent dyes and nanoparticles, which make it possible to measure fluid movements evoked by sound.

Of relevance here is the fact that the cochlea has an opening at the apex, which provides an outlet for the perfusion medium as well as allowing visualization of cochlear structures. Previous studies showed that this opening reduces the effective sound pressure level for frequencies below 200 Hz (10) but above this frequency, the opening has no effect. Fortunately, the best frequency of the cochlear location studied here is close to 200 Hz.

Another consideration is whether the opening at the apex changes fundamental characteristics of the fluid motion, and not just its low-frequency amplitude. We conclude that it does not: When the cochlea is opened, the fluid in scala vestibuli is connected to the immersion fluid outside, without impedance discontinuities. This opening therefore acts as an absorber, but unnatural reflections are not created, in contrast to a cochlea with an apical opening that faces air. Consistent with this notion, we have not observed the kind of notches in the frequency response expected to be produced by an altered pattern of sound reflections.

Fluorescence correlation spectroscopy

To measure cochlear fluid motion, we use fluorescence correlation spectroscopy (FCS, *e.g.* 11). In FCS, a confocal microscope is used to track the motion of individual fluorescent molecules present at nanomolar concentrations. As the fluorescent molecules diffuse, they will randomly move in and out of the microscope's detection volume. Molecules inside the volume are excited by a focused laser beam and emit light, increasing the count rate at the

detector. If the molecule is moving slowly, it will tend to stay for a long time in the detection volume, thus keeping the count rate stationary for a longer duration. Molecules that move faster produce shorter-duration increases in count rate when they move into the detection volume. By computing the autocorrelation of a time series of such fluorescence fluctuations, the average time that molecules spend in the detection volume can be determined (Fig. 1a). Fig. 1b shows a series of correlation curves obtained from a solution of fluorescent dextran molecules in a dish connected to a piezo-electric element driven at 200 Hz. The periodic motion of the dye molecules caused a characteristic pattern with peaks and troughs to appear in the correlation curve. These became more pronounced with increasing displacement. The correlation curves were fitted to a simplified model based on the assumption that the detection volume (V_{rel}) can be approximated with an ellipsoid:

$$V_{rel} = (1 - d)^2 \cdot \left(1 + \frac{d}{2}\right) \quad (1)$$

$$d = \min(1, |k \cdot \sin(\omega t + \varphi) - \sin(\varphi)|)$$

Here, the parameter k is proportional to the amplitude of fluid motion. Data in Fig. 1b were fitted to this model and in Fig. 1c, we plot the value of k versus the imposed displacement, which was measured with laser interferometry. Note that the points fall on the same line, indicating that fluid movements larger than approximately 55 nm can be measured with high precision. The slope of the fitted lines showed some variation across experiments, but these were minor (Fig. 1d, data from 6 individual calibration experiments; the thick dashed line shows the fit across all six experiments). This demonstrates that FCS can be used to measure nanometer displacements of fluorescent molecules moving at acoustic frequencies. However, FCS cannot reveal the direction of fluid movement.

FIGURE 1. Fluorescence correlation spectroscopy (FCS) measures the movement of fluorescent molecules. (a). In the absence of an acoustic stimulus, FCS shows the diffusion of molecules and the number of molecules in the detection volume. (b). During acoustic stimulation, peaks appear in the correlation curves at multiples of the period time of the stimulus. The height of the peaks are proportional to the amplitude of fluid movement. (c). Fitting the model in Eq. 1 to the correlation curves in panel B makes it possible to retrieve the amplitude of fluid motion. (d). In 6 different experiments, slopes showed only minor variations, demonstrating the reproducibility of such measurements.

The nanoear

A method for determining the direction of fluid movements was described by Ohlinger *et al* (12). Their “nanoear” is capable of measuring nanometer-sized fluid movements by using a laser tweezers setup. In such a setup, a microscope objective is used to focus a high-power infrared laser beam to a diffraction-limited spot. Within the focal spot, the steep gradient in light intensity creates a potential well that keeps small objects trapped in the laser focus. Such optical traps have finite stiffness, meaning that the motion of objects in the focus are restricted but not completely stopped. By measuring the Brownian movements of trapped objects, the stiffness of the trap can be directly obtained.

In our experiments, we implemented the nanoear by projecting a 2W 1064-nm Nd:YAG laser into the back of a water-immersion objective lens mounted on a Zeiss LSM780 confocal microscope. The objective lens had numerical aperture of 0.8, resulting in a relatively soft optical trap (Fig. 2). The low numerical aperture is necessary, since experiments inside the cochlea require an objective lens with long working distance. The motion of the trapped objects was tracked by a high-speed

FIGURE 2. The stiffness of the optical trap was obtained by measuring the positional variance of a trapped bead and applying the equipartition theorem. These measurements show a peak stiffness of 10.5 $\mu\text{N/m}$ at 2 W.

CMOS camera capturing 2000 – 8000 frames/s. Image acquisition was controlled by custom Labview software that ensured the acoustic stimulus and the camera were precisely synchronized.

In a typical experiment, gold nanoparticles with average diameter of 50 nm were introduced in scala media through the glass micropipette mentioned above. Once the laser was turned on, a gold particle would typically be trapped within 30 s. Having trapped a particle, the sound stimulus was started, and images of the moving bead captured by the camera. To determine the position of the bead in each image, a 2D Gaussian function was fitted to each image.

RESULTS

FCS data were acquired from 20 individual preparations. Here we show example data from a representative preparation. Figure 3a shows a confocal reflection image of the organ of Corti, illustrating the measurement positions, two of which were located in scala media (SM1 and 2 in Fig. 3a). Recordings were also made from a single position in the inner sulcus (IS), tunnel of Corti (TC) and outer tunnel (OT). Data in Fig. 3 were acquired at a stimulus frequency of 200 Hz. Fluid motions were markedly different in these locations, as shown in Fig. 3b-f.

At the center of scala media (Fig. 3b, SM1 position), fluid motion was small at 64 dB SPL but a peak was nonetheless apparent in the correlation curves, as evidenced by the minor peak at 5 ms in the blue correlation curve. Closer to the organ of Corti (SM2 position), there was no apparent peak at 64 dB SPL (blue curve in Fig. 3c), demonstrating that fluid motion in this preparation was larger at the center of scala media than it was near the organ of Corti. This difference was evident also at higher stimulus levels (74 and 84 dB SPL), where correlation curves recorded at the center of scala media exhibited sharper peaks and deeper troughs than their siblings recorded near the organ of Corti.

At the inner sulcus (Fig. 3d), fluid motion was below the detection limit at 74 dB SPL, but peaks began to appear at 84 and 94 dB SPL. The tunnel of Corti (Fig. 3e) showed the smallest fluid motion, with no recordable motion at 74 dB SPL and only a minor peak at 84 dB SPL. The outer tunnel (Fig. 3f) had slightly larger fluid motion than the inner sulcus and tunnel of Corti, but still substantially smaller than the SM2 position.

To quantify these fluid movements, correlation curves were fitted with the model described in Eq. 1. The value of the k parameter was then used to retrieve the absolute amplitude of fluid motion by using the averaged calibration shown by the thick dashed line in Fig. 1d.

At the center of scala media (SM1 position, Fig. 3b), fluid motion increased with the stimulus level, from 103 nm at 64 dB SPL to 304 nm at 74 dB SPL. At 84 dB SPL, the fit returned a value of 1630 nm. This may reflect true expansive nonlinearity or uncertainties in the curve fits that were commonly seen at high stimulus levels. Developing better fitting models is a priority.

Near the organ of Corti (SM2 position, Fig. 3c), fluid motion was below the detection limit at 64 dB SPL, but at 74 dB SPL, we recorded a motion amplitude of 150 nm. For stimulation at 84 dB SPL, fluid motion was 513 nm.

These data suggest fluid motion amplitudes are about 6 dB larger at the center of scala media than they are at positions close to the organ of Corti. However, such a difference was not present in the laser tweezers data (see below).

For the inner sulcus, fluid movement at 84 dB SPL was 9 dB smaller than the SM2 position at the same sound pressure (180 nm vs. 513 nm). At the tunnel of Corti, the magnitude of fluid motion was 109 nm at 84 dB SPL, increasing to 340 nm at 94 dB. Thus, tunnel of Corti fluid motion at 94 dB SPL had approximately the same magnitude

FIGURE 3. Fluid movements differ in various parts of the inner ear. (a). Confocal reflection image of the apical organ of Corti with measurement positions superimposed. (b). Correlation curves acquired midway between Reissner's membrane and the organ of Corti (SM1 position). (c-f) Correlation curves acquired at SM2, IS, TC and OT positions. Peaks near 5 ms lag time are caused by the fluid motion that occurs during presentation of the 200-Hz acoustic stimulus.

as the SM1 position at 74 dB SPL, implying a 20-dB magnitude difference between the structures. At the outer tunnel, fluid movements were 203 nm and 550 nm at 84 and 94 dB SPL, respectively. This means that the outer tunnel fluid motion magnitude is 14 dB below the center of scala media (SM1 position) and approximately 8 dB below SM2. In terms of magnitudes, the positions are ordered as follows: SM1 > SM2 > OT = IS > TC. The data are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE 1. Magnitudes of fluid motion (in nanometers) at different sound pressure levels. Refer to Fig. 3 for explanations of anatomical structures.

Sound pressure level	SM1	SM2	IS	TC	OT
64 dB SPL	103	<55			
74 dB SPL	304	150	<55	<55	<55
84 dB SPL	1630	513	180	109	203
94 dB SPL			820	340	550

Direction of fluid movement in scala media

Although FCS is sensitive to the nanometer motion of fluorescent molecules, it cannot measure the direction of motion in its standard configuration. Such measurements however become feasible in a laser tweezers setup. Since the stiffness of the trap is known (Fig. 2), the force acting on the bead during acoustic stimulation can be calculated, and by extension from this, the local sound power. Fig. 4 shows example data. In this experiment, beads were trapped at three different positions inside scala media, at a laser power of 2000 mW. Measurements at stimulation level of 88 dB SPL were repeated three times at position #1, eight times at position #2, and twice at position #3. The direction of the fluid motion trajectories was consistent, with the main axis directed approximately perpendicular to the reticular lamina. Their amplitude was also consistent: 224 ± 81 nm (mean ± 1 sd), 221 ± 78 nm, and 220 ± 4 nm.

The trap stiffness of $10.4 \mu\text{N/m}$ at 2000 mW implies that these bead movements were caused by a force of 2.3 pN acting on the bead. To place this number in context, we follow the approach of Ohlinger *et al* (12), who showed that the average acoustic power acting on a bead in an optical trap can be estimated from the bead's maximum displacement x_{max} , provided that the stiffness κ of the trap is known:

$$P_{\text{detected}} = \frac{1}{2\pi} c \rho \left(\frac{\kappa x_{\text{max}}}{6\eta} \right)^2 \quad (2)$$

where η is the dynamic viscosity, c is the speed of sound, and ρ is the density of water. For a maximum displacement of 220 nm, this results in a detected sound power level of -14 dB SWL at the bead's location in the cochlea in response to an acoustic stimulus at 88 dB SPL.

DISCUSSION

The results of this study can be summarized as follows:

1. Sound-evoked fluid movements can be measured with FCS or in a laser tweezers setup. FCS measurements can be performed at locations inside the organ of Corti, while laser tweezers measure the force exerted by an acoustic stimulus on a trapped object.

FIGURE 4. (a) Reflection confocal image with measurement locations superimposed. (b). Bead motion in response to a 200-Hz tone at 88 dB SPL at position #1. (c). Bead motion for the same stimulus as in (b), but recorded 8 times somewhat closer to Reissner's membrane (position #2). (d). Bead motion at position #3.

In this experiment, beads were trapped at three different positions inside scala media, at a laser power of 2000 mW. Measurements at stimulation level of 88 dB SPL were repeated three times at position #1, eight times at position #2, and twice at position #3. The direction of the fluid motion trajectories was consistent, with the main axis directed approximately perpendicular to the reticular lamina. Their amplitude was also consistent: 224 ± 81 nm (mean ± 1 sd), 221 ± 78 nm, and 220 ± 4 nm.

2. Fluid movements are larger in the fluid surrounding the organ of Corti than they are inside. The tunnel of Corti shows fluid movements about 20 dB smaller than the surrounding fluid, whereas the outer tunnel is 14 dB below the surrounding fluid. Movements recorded in the inner sulcus are similar to the ones in the outer tunnel.
3. The sound power level in scala media is -14 dB SWL for an acoustic stimulus at 88 dB SPL. The same stimulus exerts a force of a few pN on a trapped bead.

It makes intuitive sense to have small fluid movements inside the organ of Corti, since any motion of the internal fluid requires energy to be used solely for pushing the fluid around. By not moving this fluid, the system becomes more energetically effective.

We were surprised by the small stimulus-related force recorded inside scala media. For instance, we note that the bundle of stereocilia on mouse hair cells has an aggregate stiffness of approximately 5 mN/m (13). Thus, the 2.3-pN force recorded in the fluid would suffice to displace a hair bundle by 0.46 nm. It thus seems that acoustic forces in the fluid are quite small even for a relatively loud stimulus. The unexpectedly small forces exerted by the fluid are also evident from the low sound power level of -14 dB SWL at the bead's location in scala media. These low values lead us to question the mechanism whereby the apical organ of Corti is excited.

A traditional view, supported by direct measurements of sound-evoked pressures at the base of the cochlea (6), is that the organ of Corti is excited by the pressure difference across the basilar membrane. We do not question the operation of such a mechanism in the high-frequency areas of the cochlea. However, at the apex only a small region of the basilar membrane vibrates in response to sound (2), a finding that does not appear to be compatible with the classical mechanism. Based on this previous finding and the small pressures and forces recorded here, we propose that waves propagating within the structure of the organ of Corti from sites located closer to the base are also important for exciting the organ of Corti at the apex, and not only the local pressure gradient across the organ of Corti.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Jont Allen]: So you said you calibrated it, and you believe the calibration was working fine, but then when you put it inside the cochlea, it was no longer calibrated and you do not know what the error was. Can you re-do this in an

artificial volume where you know what's going on? There must be some way of compensating for the fact that it's being held, the fluid is being constrained by the walls.

[**Anders Fridberger**]: The problem in the cochlea is that the laser beam has to traverse Reissner's membrane to reach the bead, also the opening in the cochlea is relatively small so it will cut off a part of the beam, meaning that the stiffness of the trap is reduced. We have a few calibrations from inside the cochlea, and they show a trap stiffness which is 30 – 50% of the value that we get in a dish. But the calibrations are quite time-consuming, because you need really long time stretches of bead movements to be sure of the variance, which is the critical parameter here. So that's why I'm mentioning the other calibration, rather than the one we did inside the cochlea.

[**Jont Allen**]: Changing the frequency won't help?

[**Anders Fridberger**]: The calibrations are done by observing the Brownian motion of the bead, so there is no acoustic stimulus.

[**Hannes** (inaudible surname)]: So I was wondering, you are showing results with only one frequency. Have you changed the frequency, and do the motion patterns change when you do so?

[**Anders Fridberger**]: The best frequency of the location is approximately 200 Hz, and this is why we chose this frequency. We have some measurements at other frequencies, they are similar to the ones I showed here, but of course the amplitude differs a bit.

[**Dáibhid Ó Maoiléidigh**]: So you compare the force you measure to hair bundle stiffness but you did not measure the fluid motion near the hair bundles. Do you have plans to do that, and how do you think this fluid force may vary for different locations?

[**Anders Fridberger**]: One of the original goals of this project was to measure fluid flows in the subretrochlear space. Now it turns out that at the apex of the guinea pig cochlea, there isn't much of a subretrochlear space. We never managed to get any beads into this hypothetical space, and also, we could not record reliable FCS curves there. The reason for this is seen in many of the reflection images that we get. There simply is no space under the tectorial membrane at the apex.

[**Dáibhid Ó Maoiléidigh**]: But there are hair bundles?

[**Anders Fridberger**]: Of course!

[**Dáibhid Ó Maoiléidigh**]: OK, thank you.

[**Anna Wisniowiecki**]: Thank you for this great paper. I am very interested in the techniques and potential towards measuring fluid dynamics in the cochlea. The investigation of differing response from base to apex is also fascinating. A few questions about your method and results:

-I am not very familiar with FCS. What are the challenges related to fitting the measurement curves? I was also wondering, what limits the smallest displacement that can be measured using FCS? Is it known whether the displacement sensitivity allows for capturing the range of fluid motion in cochlea?

-In your FCS results, you observe that the measured displacement is low near the organ of Corti (closer to the outer tunnel) relative to the center of the scala media. This makes me think about whether these measurements could be reflecting the boundary condition of a Poiseuille flow.

-Does the presence of the optical trap disturb the local fluid flow? I assume so since it creates a local pressure. In the center of the scala media where the longitudinal flow is greatest, I imagine the optical trap would yield accurate results. However, I wonder whether, near the boundaries of the scala media (and near the organ of Corti), where the velocity may be reduced, the optical trap could cause a change in the local flow, even causing vortices.

-Considering that your displacement vector measured with the optical tweezers shows similar amplitudes and trajectories at all 3 scala media locations, do you think that this could reflect the transverse oscillation of the organ of Corti?

We have injected nanoparticles in the mouse cochlea and visualized their flow with OCT over small time scales in our group. Perhaps, this could be used to clarify the overall flow field in the cochlear cross-section.

[Anders Fridberger]:

-The problem with the curve fitting is that you need a mathematical model that describes the effect of the oscillating fluid flow on the correlation curve. There is only one paper in the literature on this, and the authors of that paper write that their model did not provide a good fit. The model we have works reasonably well, but the residuals are often substantial.

-The sensitivity of an FCS measurement depends on the concentration of the fluorophore (lower concentrations gives curves with higher amplitude) but at low concentrations, you also get a lower count rate. And more photons counted translates into less noise in the correlation curves. The numerical aperture of the objective lens also has great influence. To make good measurements, it is necessary to find a balance between these factors. In our experiments, we are able to detect motions down to approximately 50 nm.

-The idea of the smaller motion near the organ of Corti reflecting Poiseuille flow is very interesting. I cannot say for sure what is going on at this point, but the suggestion is definitely interesting.

-The optical trap holds the bead through forces exerted by light and the bead is small, around 50 nm. So I do not think it should cause any significant disturbance of the overall flow pattern.

-As to your last question, we have measurements at different angles of observation but these have not yet been processed. Once this is done, I can hopefully answer the question.

[Dennis Freeman]: These novel measurements of sound-induced fluid motions of cochlear structures in the apex are very interesting. While these studies were motivated by an interest in characterizing cochlear mechanics in the apex, some of your results could conceivably also apply in the base. Could you comment on the possibility of making similar measurements in the base?

[Anders Fridberger]: To measure fluid flow with FCS, the Péclet number has to be greater than 1, otherwise only the diffusion of the fluorophore can be detected. The number is calculated by taking (the radius of the detection volume x fluid velocity) / diffusion coefficient of the fluorophore. At the base, fluid velocities are likely to be higher, which is an advantage. Provided that an objective lens with sufficient numerical aperture, at least 0.8, can be brought into position close to the base, there should be no problem.